

Detection of Essential and Non-Essential Metals in Dorsal Muscles and Skin of Bulte Tuna the Local Caught from Misurata Coast

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Abstract

The content of five heavy metals (zinc, copper, iron, cadmium and lead) in muscles and skin has been studied for one most consumed fish species (*Auxis rochei*, Risso, 1810) from the Mediterranean Sea coast of Libya Misurata. The metals content of muscles and skin were determined by an inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) (Agilent 200 Series AA-Agilent Technologies, Assembly Fume Extraction, Part No.: 210190000, Serial No.: MY14520002). The current study, it has been shown that the skin of *Auxis Rochei* has registered the highest concentration of Zn, while Fe was found to be highest in the muscles. On the other hand, the lowest contents of Cd and Pb were recorded in both muscles and skin. The arrangement of metallic elements in the studied tissues followed the following sequence: iron > copper > zinc > lead > cadmium. However, in the skin tissue, the sequence was reversed with zinc first, followed by iron > copper > lead > cadmium. The values obtained from metal detection in the muscles and skin of fish in the current study were below the limits allowed by FAO/WHO and EFSA. Conclusions The current results show that fish is one of the most indicative factors for estimating trace metals pollution in marine systems. Therefore, monitoring and analyzing fish populations is necessary to safeguard both the environment and public health.

Keywords: *Metals, Muscles, Skin, Bulte tuna, Misurata.*

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Introduction

Global environmental pollution is considered a multifaceted international human health concern, where environmental pollution is regarded as the disruption of normal environmental functions. This issue has garnered significant attention in recent years due to its detrimental impact on both the natural world and human populations. The unprecedented rate at which pollutants are being released into the environment has led to widespread degradation of air, water, and soil quality. The consequences of this disruption extend beyond ecological damage and pose severe risks to human health. Exposure to pollutants such as toxic chemicals, heavy metals, and airborne particulate matter has been associated with various diseases including respiratory illnesses, cancer, neurological disorders, and reproductive problems (Njinkoue et al., 2016; Chinedu and Chukwuemeka, 2018).

The high demand for fish is not only attributed to its delectable taste, but also largely due to its exceptional nutritional values, which are a direct result of its proximate composition. Fish is rich in essential nutrients such as protein, omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins, and minerals. These components contribute significantly to the overall health benefits associated with consuming fish regularly (Njinkoue et al., 2016). The maintenance of acid-base balance is one of the crucial functions performed by essential metals in the body. Furthermore, these minerals also play a vital role in the formation of hemoglobin such as iron (Fe) (Duran and Tuzen, 2010). In addition to, copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn) are vital for the growth and metabolism of living organisms. This essential metal is crucial for various biological processes and must be carefully managed in living systems (Zoroddu et al., 2019). In the case of Zn, a deficiency in the diet can lead to various dermal problems, as well as retardation of growth and sexual maturation. It is important to note that these effects occur due to the essential role that zinc plays in numerous physiological processes within the body. Therefore, ensuring an adequate intake of zinc through a balanced diet or appropriate supplementation is crucial for maintaining optimal health and development (Kaim et al., 2013). Copper deficiency can lead to arterial weakness, liver problems, and anemia. While these metals are essential, fish have the ability to accumulate them. When their concentrations surpass the toxicity threshold or permissible limits, they can pose potential harm to humans (Noman et al., 2022). In contrast, essential metals can become toxic to fish when present in high concentrations, as highlighted by Gulec et al. (2011).

Heavy metals are a group of non-essential metals and metalloids that possess an atomic density exceeding 4 grams per cubic centimeter (g/cm³). These elements, including lead, mercury, cadmium, arsenic, and others, are commonly referred to as heavy metals due to their high atomic masses. Although present in minute concentrations within biological systems, they exert significant impacts on human health and the environment (Muzyed, 2011).

Fish have the ability to readily accumulate heavy metals in their bodies from sediment, water, or food due to their position in the aquatic food chain. This phenomenon is a cause for concern as heavy metal contamination poses various risks to both human health and the overall ecosystem. Therefore, it is crucial for researchers and regulatory agencies to closely monitor and regulate the levels of heavy metals present in fish populations (Zhao et al., 2012).

The level of heavy metal bioaccumulation in fish tissues is influenced by various biotic and abiotic factors. Biotic factors include the fish's biological habitat, age, gender, body mass and physiologic condition. Abiotic factors such as the chemical form of metal in the water, water temperature and pH value, dissolved oxygen concentration, and water transparency also play a significant role. Understanding these factors is crucial for assessing the potential risks associated with heavy metal contamination in aquatic ecosystems (Has-Schçn et al., 2006). According to Emon et al. (2023), the bioaccumulation of toxic heavy metals (Non-Essential metals) from a contaminated environment in several important organs of fish has disturbed their normal functions. This phenomenon has had severe effects on the normal physiology of fish, leading to reduced growth and reproduction.

The amount of metals in the different muscle tissues of fish is limited (Bosch et al., 2016; Charette et al., 2021). The teleostean fish has two types of muscles, red and white. The red myotomal muscle fibers in most fish are arranged as being parallel to the longitudinal axis of the body in one or more surface bands, while the white fibers constitute most of the musculature and follow complex helicoidal trajectory in successive myotomes. Intermediate or pink is a third type of muscle in some species, their fibers are distributed between the red and white muscles (Gill et al., 1998; Charette et al., 2021).

Bullet tuna (*Auxis rochei*, Risso, 1810) was Synonyms *Scomber rochei* Risso, 1810 (Froese et al., 2024). Distributes this fish *Auxis rochei* in Atlantic, Indian and Pacific (Western) and the Mediterranean Sea (Allaya, 2013). Fish of *Auxis rochei* has been seen in the coastal areas of Tunisian waters. Furthermore, found it costal of Misurata city, which caught by fishers in February 2024, during collecting samples this appear.

The objectives of this study are measure the concentrations of iron (Fe), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd) in fish dorsal muscles. This will allow us to determine the extent of any heavy metal contamination present in these fish. Secondly, to establish a correlation between metal concentrations and fish weight and length.

Materials and Methods

Sample

Fish samples were collected from Sea fishing port of Misurata city, during the autumn of 2024. A total of five fish (Fig.1) were carefully selected from various locations within this region for the purpose of this study. The mean weight and length were 0.09 ± 0.03 g, 39.54 ± 1.24 cm (Frock length, FL) and 35.44 ± 0.29 cm (Standard length) respectively. The collected samples were stored in a cooler packed with ice and were sent immediately to the laboratory (Zoology laboratory, 1 at Faculty of science, Misurata university) for the dissection of the muscles after removing the scales and washed thoroughly.

Heavy Metals Analysis

Muscle samples were taken from each individual fish for the determination of the concentration of each of the metals under consideration, with each sample weighing 1 g. Samples were frozen at -20 °C until their analysis.

The sampling was carried out in accordance with the European protection rules for animals used for scientific purposes (European Parliament, 2010). Essential and non-essential metals analyzed were as follows: iron (Fe), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd). For their detection, an inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) (Agilent 200 Series AA-Agilent Technologies, Assembly Fume Extraction, Part No.: 210190000, Serial No.: MY14520002) was used. Each sample was homogenized and digested in a digestion solution (15 mL, with 65% nitric acid (HNO₃) and hydrogen peroxide) and heated on a plate at 200 °C. When the sample reached a volume of 5 mL, the content was

decanted into beaker and diluted in deionized until reaching 30 mL. The resulting product was filtered using filter paper placed in a funnel, in order to obtain a pure output.

Figure 1. Sampling Areas for Dorsal Muscle (DM) from Auxis Rochei (Risso, 1810)
Note: Standard (SL) and Fork length

Statistical Analysis

The concentrations of metals in fish tissues were reported as ppm. T-tests were used to evaluate differences between weight and length. A p-value less than (0.05) was considered to be statistically significant. All statistical analyses were done using the computer program of SPSS Inc. (2007, version 16.0 for Windows XP).

Results

The present study has yielded significant findings regarding the concentration of essential and non-essential metals in the muscles and skin of fish. Analysis of Table (1) indicates a notable increase in the average level of Fe (88.32 ± 8.02 ppm) compared to Zn (65.39 ± 10.96 ppm) and Cu (33.86 ± 5.51 ppm) in Auxis Rochei's muscles. Moreover, a decrease was observed in the average concentrations of non-essential metals, specifically Cd compared to Pb (0.05 ± 0.02 and 0.69 ± 0.53 ppm, respectively), within the fish muscles of A.Rochei.

Table 1. Mean Values of Heavy Metals (ppm) in Auxis Rochei (Risso, 1810) Muscles

Metals	(Mean \pm SE)	
	Muscles	Skin
Zn	65.39 ± 10.96	271.24 ± 34.43
Cu	33.86 ± 5.51	15.605 ± 3.91
Fe	88.32 ± 8.02	82.61 ± 10.21
Cd	0.05 ± 0.02	0.059 ± 0.02
Pb	0.69 ± 0.53	1.76 ± 0.19

The present study conducted revealed a significant increase in the average levels of Zn (271.24 ± 34.43 ppm) compared to Fe (82.61 ± 10.21 ppm) and Cu (15.605 ± 3.91 ppm) in the skin of Auxis Rochei. Conversely, there was a noticeable decrease in non-essential metals such as Cd, as opposed to Pb (0.059 ± 0.02 ppm and 1.76 ± 0.19 ppm respectively), in skin of *A. Rochei* according to Table 1 findings. Additionally, Figure 2 demonstrates distinct variations in mean values of both essential and non-essential

metals between muscles and skin of *A. Rochei*. Zn exhibited significantly higher concentrations ($P > 0.01$) than Fe, Cu, Pb, and Cd respectively.

The figure (2) illustrates the high value of zinc, comparable between the muscles and skin of fish in this study. The disparity in zinc values indicates a significant level of significance at a p-value less than 0.05. Additionally, it was observed that there is a significant difference in copper values between the muscles and skin, with a p-value greater than 0.05 (Figure 2). However, no significant difference was noted in the iron values between the muscles and skin (p-value greater than 0.05). The findings from this study suggest that non-essential metals exhibit varying mean values in both the muscles and skin of *A. Rochei* (Figure 1). Furthermore, there was no significant presence of cadmium in either muscles or skin (p-value less than 0.05), whereas lead showed significant levels (p-value less than 0.05).

Figure 2. Mean Concentration of Heavy Metals (ppm) in *Auxis rochei* (Risso, 1810) muscles

Discussion

Metals like zinc, copper and iron are essential for fish metabolism while some others such as cadmium and lead have are non-essential in biological systems. In order to maintain normal metabolism, fish must uptake essential metals from water, food, or sediment. However, non-essential metals are also taken up by fish and accumulate in their tissues.

The currently study shown that, mean concentrations of both essential and non-essential metals in muscles and skin of fish species showed great variations. The current study has indicated that Zn concentrations were the highest in skin, Fe and Cu in muscles of *Auxis rochei*, with some exceptions of Zn in muscles, Cu and Fe in skin were lowest concentration, these results being consistent with the findings of Bashir and alhemmal (2015) suggested in his study on *Pennahia anea* and *Arius maculatus*. In addition to studying Hasan et al. (2022) on *Systomus sarana*, *Pethia ticto* and *Mastacembelus armatus*.

The higher level of zinc in the skin is due to the fact that muscles are not an active site for metal biotransformation. Similar results were found with Raka et al. (2020).

The essential metals, such as zinc, copper, and iron are in higher values, presumably due to their function as co-factors for the activation of a number of enzymes and regulated to maintain a certain homeostatic status in fish (El-Batrawy et al., 2018). Zn is an essential micronutrient that plays a significant role in the

growth and reproduction of fish (Bryan and Langston, 1992; UNEP, 1993) and Zn deficiency in fish has been found to exacerbate the effects of fin and skin erosion, as well as increase their susceptibility to toxic elements like arsenic (Raka et al., 2020). In addition to Cu is an essential trace element and micronutrient, important for the growth and metabolism of living organisms. In fish and other vertebrates, copper is the key constituent of many metabolic enzymes and glycoprotein. It is also essential for haemoglobin synthesis and nervous system function (Panagos et al., 2018).

In this study, on average, accumulation of Zn in skin > muscles, while muscles > skin for Fe and Cu. These results similar finding of Manisalidis et al. (2020). The distribution of heavy metals in fish samples analyzed were in muscles: Fe > Zn > Cu, while Zn > Fe > Cu in Skin. The differences in metal accumulation in fish tissues are conditioned by a complex of factors, which are determined by the intensity of plastic and generative metabolism of fish. Therefore, fish specimens possess a regulatory mechanism for essential elements (Zn, Cu and Fe) uptake (Firat and Kargin 2010, Zubcov et al., 2012), but there is no doubt that a linkage exists between trace element accumulation level in fish organs and its content in the environment.

The metal concentrations in muscles and skin (Edible tissues) of the examined fish were compared to different international concentrations. The level of zinc, Copper and iron were below the acceptable limit recommended by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (10–100 mg/kg Cu and 30– 100 mg/kg Zn) according to FAO/WHO (1998). In addition to, the level of Cd and Pb were below the acceptable limit recommended by EFSA (2007) (0. 1 mg/kg wet weight and 0. 3 mg/kg wet weight for Cd and Pb respectively).

Conclusion

In this work, an assessment was done on the patterns of Zn, Cu, Fe, Cd and Pb accumulation in *Auxis rochei* (Risso, 1810) from Scombridae families from the Mediterranean sea coast of Libya Misurata. Investigations have been carried out on organs and tissues (Muscles and skin) of fish, in accordance to season capture, length and weight. The highest concentration of zinc was registered in the skin of *A. rochei*, and of Fe in the muscles. The lowest Cd and Pb contents were recorded in the muscles and skin of *A. rochei*.

The current results demonstrate that fish represent one of the most indicative factors for the estimation of trace metals pollution in marine systems. This finding is crucial not only for the protection of the environment but also for ensuring the quality of human consumption. Recognizing fish as a reliable indicator helps us assess and address potential risks associated with trace metals contamination effectively. Therefore, it is imperative to monitor and analyze fish populations regularly to safeguard both ecosystems and public health. Moreover, this study being one of the most important steps in the monitoring of the ecology of the marine.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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